

Environmental Data Science Innovation & Inclusion Lab

ESIL Forest Carbon CodeFest 2024 Evaluation Report

Prepared by Margaret Hegwood, Megan K. Littrell, Anne U. Gold, and Emily Ward

University of Colorado Boulder

May 2024

This work is funded by the National Science Foundation.
NSF Award Number DBI-2153040.

Contents

Program Description and Evaluation Methodology	4
Program Description	4
Evaluation Methodology	4
Executive Summary	5
Pre-CodeFest Training Evaluation	5
CodeFest Evaluation (March 12 – 14, 2024)	5
Highlights of the ESIL CodeFest	6
Respondents’ Recommendations for Improvement to the ESIL CodeFest	7
ESIL Engagement and CodeFest Goals	8
Participants’ Goals for the CodeFest	8
CodeFest Attendee Characteristics	9
CodeFest Attendance and Survey Participation	9
Participant Demographic Information	9
Education, Career Experience, and Affiliation	10
Accommodations for Attendees	11
Pre-CodeFest Trainings Evaluation	11
Respondents’ Recommendation for Improving Pre-CodeFest Trainings	12
2024 Forest Carbon CodeFest Evaluation Outcomes	13
Participant Satisfaction with the ESIL CodeFest	13
CodeFest Overall Highlights	14
Networking Connections and Collaboration	16
Overall Learning and Use of Data Tools and Skills	17
Confidence in Working with Data Skills and Tools	18
Experience Working with Data Cubes	19
	2

Concepts, Data Skills, Tools, and Workflows Acquired	20
Sense of Belonging in the EDS Communities	21
Culture of Inclusion: General Respect and Respect for Expertise	22
Group/Team Dynamics	24
CodeFest Artists in Residence	25
Participant Reflections on the CodeFest Theme	26
CodeFest Overall Impacts and Innovation	27
References	28
Appendix: Evaluation Surveys	29

Program Description and Evaluation Methodology

Program Description

The Environmental Data Science Innovation and Inclusion Lab (ESIIL, www.esiil.org) serves as a data science center of excellence and synthesis center that facilitates collaboration across large, diverse teams through the ESIIL Network. ESIIL brings together a diverse community of environmental and biological data scientists to turn environmental and biological data into actionable understanding and knowledge toward a more sustainable society. The center activities support ESIIL's mission: "*Empower an inclusive and diverse community to accelerate continental-scale environmental data science (EDS)*".

This report summarizes the evaluation feedback on the **Forest Carbon CodeFest**, which took place in at the University of Colorado Boulder from March 12-14, 2024. The CodeFest aimed to bring together diverse teams who used cyberinfrastructure and curated data sets to explore their own scientific questions investigating aboveground forest carbon dynamics as they relate to wildfires and other forest disturbances. Code developed during the ESIIL coding events including the Forest Carbon CodeFest will create open, reproducible workflows needed for further refinement into data tools for integration into the ESIIL cyberinfrastructure and for use by the ESIIL Network.

Pre-CodeFest Trainings. Prior to the event, participants were invited to take part in three virtual pre-event trainings designed to help participants begin collaborating with similar levels of background knowledge and skills. The trainings included:

- Introduction, teamwork, open science, and data sovereignty (Feb. 21)
- Skills for cloud-based collaboration (Feb. 28)
- Data availability and forest carbon perspectives (Mar. 7)

Evaluation Methodology

The evaluation team used a collaborative approach (King and Stevahn 2013, Shulha et al. 2016) to design evaluation activities for all ESIIL coding events, meeting with the coding event organizers to discuss survey development prior to the associated events. For the Forest Carbon CodeFest, an online, evaluation pre-survey was sent to all registered attendees the week before the event. On the final day of the event, attendees were invited to take an online reflection survey to share their experiences.

ESIIL Program evaluation is co-led by Anne U. Gold, Megan K. Littrell, and Emily Ward. This study has been approved by the University of Colorado Institutional Research Board (IRB) Protocol 23-0162. Funding for this work was provided by the National Science Foundation (NSF, Award #DBI-2153040). Any opinions, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the author and do not necessarily reflect the views of the NSF.

Executive Summary

Pre-CodeFest Training Evaluation

More than **75%** of respondents **agreed** or **strongly agreed** that the one or more of the pre-training events on Introduction, **Teamwork, open science, and data** (Feb. 21), **Skills for cloud-based collaboration** (Feb. 28), and **Data availability and forest carbon perspectives** (Mar. 7) prepared them for the CodeFest.¹

To improve the trainings, respondents suggested extending the event's duration and providing more in-depth, mandatory training sessions. Respondents also discussed challenges for individuals without certain technologies, like dual monitors, and advocated for training methods that account for these differences. They also highlighted the need for better pre-event preparation, such as developing individual research questions, improved communication on technical requirements, and creating groups based on interests to enhance collaboration. Lastly, offering detailed written instructions with supplemental office hours could be more effective for technical learning.

CodeFest Evaluation (March 12 – 14, 2024)

78% of respondents overall were either **extremely satisfied** (50%) or **satisfied** (28%) with the CodeFest.

50% of respondents expressed that they were **motivated to continue working on the ideas that were explored during the CodeFest** to a very large (12%) or large (41%) extent.

75% agreed overall that **working with artists enhanced their overall experience**.

Culture of Inclusion: A large majority of respondents (76%) agreed that colleagues' showed a **general respect for each other** and that ideas were **valued** (65%). A notable portion of respondents (**65%**) also agreed that all group members **felt comfortable providing feedback and contributing opposing viewpoints**.

Group Dynamics:

Mentors and Judges: **87%** of respondents agreed that their **mentors provided helpful guidance** throughout the CodeFest. **74%** of respondents agreed that the **judges provided helpful feedback**, and **81%** of respondents agreed that the **judges provided a fair assessment of each group's project**.

¹ Icons in the Executive Summary provided by the Noun Project's creators: Ahmad, Chimol, Deylotus Creative Design, Eko Purnomo, IconStock, Muhammad Sukirman, Nangicon, Rinaros 79, Setyo Ari Wibowo, Siti Nurhayati, and Sundari, and yieshazea2.

Team Members: 82% of respondents agreed that their **team worked well together** and that their **team had sufficient expertise to meet their goals**.

Networking Connections and Collaboration

83% of respondents **agreed (50%) or strongly agreed (33%)** that they felt better prepared for **community-building and knowledge exchanges** after participating in the CodeFest and that the event inspired them to **promote inclusion in scientific spaces and communities**.

95% of respondents indicated that they felt they had made **connections with the EDS community** and **connections across disciplines and sectors** during the CodeFest.

39% of respondents reported that they had made **connections with the AI community** and **Community Partners** during the CodeFest.

Highlights of the ESIL CodeFest

Key Themes	Highlights
Networking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meeting others in the field/industry • Collaboration and making friends, including meeting different people from across the country
Learning and Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning about remote sensing tools (e.g., Google Earth Engine, QGIS) • Diving into new research questions • In-depth insight into forest ecology through presentations
Team Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective collaboration within teams • Shared ideas and problem-solving in groups
Event Organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leadership from the program coordinator • Timely emails and instructions from the support team • Structured approach for learning coding • Dietary needs were easily accommodated
Resources and Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to Cyverse • Various informative presentations
Diversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversity of attendees and perspectives

Respondents' Recommendations for Improvement to the ESIL CodeFest

Key Themes	Highlights
Time Constraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Event was too short for effective engagement• Needed more days for focused work• Time constraints hindered research and collaboration
Team Dynamics	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Difficulties in team collaboration due to different perspectives, experience levels, and interests• Challenges in aligning on a realistic research question
Technical and Tool Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Data access issues, especially with external files and permissions• Challenges with CyVerse, such as establishing work and maintaining connection
Event Structure and Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Pre-event virtual meetings were helpful but insufficient• Guest speaker presentations ran over time, reducing work time on projects
Skill and Role Alignment	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Mismatch in coding skills within teams, affecting collaboration• Personal challenges in adapting to team's dominant programming language
Financial Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Complications with travel expense reimbursements, leading to double taxation

ESIL Engagement and CodeFest Goals

CodeFest participants were asked to indicate how they learned about the CodeFest. Most respondents heard about the CodeFest via word of mouth (41%) and other channels (24%), such as their university's email list or through participating in previous ESIL workshops.

Before the CodeFest, we asked students to also respond to an open-ended questions: *What would you like to get out of your participation in the ESIL Forest Carbon CodeFest?*

Participants' Goals for the CodeFest

Key Themes	Summary
Research and Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboratively develop productive research objectives and produce results • Brainstorm interesting research questions and hypotheses, producing preliminary results • Push the limits of scale and performance in ML-based mapping, create novel products for OSS or blogs
Networking and Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network to learn about trending problems in ecology and forestry • Meet and connect with people from diverse backgrounds and potential collaborators • Build connections in the remote sensing space
Learning Advanced Technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn about GitHub, cloud computing, geoscientific Python applications • Gain familiarity with new datasets and cloud-based data science skills • Improve ability to work with data in computational contexts

Key Themes	Summary
Career and Professional Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connect with industry professionals, possibly making connections for future jobs • Meet people working in forest carbon and related fields, have fun • Gain more experience with specific tools like CyVerse, learn about EO data products and modeling
Environmental Science and Application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand forest carbon dynamics, carbon sequestration, especially under disturbance conditions • Learn how environmental scientists leverage computing and data, including machine learning • Develop and share methods to monitor carbon in forests using limited data

CodeFest Attendee Characteristics

CodeFest Attendance and Survey Participation

There were 28 people who participated in the CodeFest. There were 16 participants completed the CodeFest Pre-Survey (57% response rate) and 18 completed the CodeFest Reflection survey (64% response rate). All CodeFest participants included in the survey reported that they live in the U.S.. Survey respondents represented attendees from nine U.S. States (Florida, Massachusetts, New Mexico, Colorado, Utah, Illinois, California, Michigan, and Missouri).

Participant Demographic Information

Survey respondents identified as follows: 50% identified as Women, and 50% identified as Men.

Gender Identity	
50%	Women
50%	Men

Most respondents identified as White, Caucasian, European, or European American (75%) and the remaining participants identified as Asian or Asian American (25%).

Race and Ethnicity*	
75%	White, Caucasian, European, or European American
25%	Asian or Asian American
0%	Black, African American, or African
0%	American Indian or Alaska Native
0%	Hispanic, Latinx; Hispanic or Latinx American
0%	I prefer not to answer
0%	More than one selection

6% of respondents identified as having a disability or as being neurodiverse. 19% of respondents identified as LGBTQ+; 6% of attendees preferred not to answer this question. There were no respondents who were members of the U.S. Armed Forces. 75% of respondents reported having parents or guardians with a Bachelor's degree or higher.

Highest Level of Education	
50%	Doctoral degree
30%	Master's degree
20%	Bachelor's degree

Education, Career Experience, and Affiliation

About one third of the respondents (31%) had earned a doctoral degree and 38% had a Master’s degree while 6% had done some graduate work. 25% of respondents had earned a Bachelor’s degree.

Field of Study: Attendees were also asked to indicate the field in which they received their highest degree. These degrees encompass a diverse range of academic disciplines, reflecting the interdisciplinary nature of Environmental Data Science (EDS), with individuals from a wide array of fields contributing to its advancement and application. One respondent reported not working in an EDS-related field.

Natural Sciences	Engineering and Applied Sciences	Social Sciences and Humanities
Environmental Science	Computer/Data Science	Social Science
Geoscience (Geology, Geography)	Engineering	
Biological science	Math	
Ecology	Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning	

Career Stage: The majority of respondents (50%) described themselves as Early Career (0 – 5 years of professional experience or a post-doctoral fellow). 13% were Mid-Career (6 – 15 years of professional experience) and 38% described themselves as students. No participants identified as late or senior career.

Affiliation: The majority of respondents reported that they work at an **Academic (higher education) institution (50%)**, followed by **Industry (13%)**. Other respondents reported that they worked at **Non-profit organizations (13%)**, **Private for-profit (13%)**, and the **Federal Government (5%)**.

Types of Academic Affiliations*	
100%	Research Intensive
44%	Undergraduate & Graduate students

*Respondents selected all that apply. Percentages add up to more than 100%.

Academic Affiliations Represented. Of those respondents working at academic institutions, the majority reported affiliation with a Research-Intensive institution (56%). Of those responses, 100% were affiliated with a research intensive institution and 44% were affiliated with institutions that served both undergraduate and graduate students. Note that there were no respondents affiliated with Community Colleges, Professional Programs, Tribal College or Tribal-serving institutions, Historically Black Colleges and Universities, Minority-serving Institutions, Hispanic-serving Institutions, or American or Native American Pacific Islander-serving Institutions.

Non-Academic Affiliations. 7 respondents (44%) indicated that they *do not* work for an academic institution. These respondents indicated that the main organizations they were affiliated with included a renewable energy/utility company, an ecosystem sciences think tank, a venture capital accelerator, an industry start up, a government funded laboratory, and a US government agency.

Primary disciplinary field(s) in Environmental Data Science (EDS): CodeFest attendees were asked to choose the primary disciplinary field(s) they work in within the broad field of EDS. The most commonly selected EDS fields selected by respondents included **Environmental Science (75%)**, **Computer/Data Science (44%)**, **GeoScience (31%)**, **Biological Science (31%)**, and **Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning (25%)**. Fewer respondents represented Math (6%) and Engineering (6%). The majority of respondents selected more than one response as their main field in EDS. Open-ended “Other” responses (6%) included: Ecology and “I don’t work in an EDS field”.

	Primary disciplinary field(s)*
75%	Environmental Science
44%	Computer/Data Science
31%	Biological Science
25%	AI/Machine Learning
6%	Math
6%	Other
31%	Geoscience
6%	Engineering

***Respondents selected all that apply. Percentages add up to more than 100%.**

Professional Society Memberships: The list of memberships included eight different professional societies: American Association of Geographers (AAG), Ecological Society of America (ESA), Sigma Xi, American Geophysical Union (AGU), American Association of Geographers (AAG), American Meteorological Society (AMS), Association for Fire Ecology, and Association for Landscape Ecology.

Accommodations for Attendees

On the pre-survey, attendees were asked to describe accommodations needed to make ESIL events as accessible as possible. No respondents indicated a need for accommodations. Although one respondent noted “ESIL has gone a long way to make accommodations for all. I have no further recommendations.”

Pre-CodeFest Trainings Evaluation

Prior to the CodeFest, attendees participated in virtual pre-CodeFest trainings, including trainings on Introduction, teamwork, open science, and data sovereignty (Feb. 21), Skills for cloud-based collaboration (Feb. 28), and Data availability and forest carbon perspectives (Mar.7). On the CodeFest Reflection survey, attendees were also asked to rate how well the trainings prepared them for the CodeFest, summarized in the graphs below.

94% of CodeFest Reflection survey respondents reported attending the pre-CodeFest trainings.

78% of respondents **agreed overall** that the training on **Introduction, teamwork, open science, and data sovereignty** and **89%** **agreed overall** the training on **Skills for cloud-based collaboration** prepared them for the CodeFest.

83% of respondents **agreed overall** that the training on **Data availability and forest carbon perspectives** prepared them for the Codefest, while 17% reported that the training did not prepare them for the event.

Respondents' Recommendation for Improving Pre-CodeFest Trainings

To improve these trainings, respondents suggested longer event duration, improved team interactions, better training delivery, more preparation for the CodeFest, changing structure, and more technical support. Below are in depth descriptions of these common themes that respondents gave, including some example quotes:

Key Themes	Recommended Improvements	Quotes
Event duration	Feedback suggests a desire for a longer event duration.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> "It was a great event and I only wish if we could do this for longer time than just 2 and a half day."
Team interaction	Participants appreciated getting to know their team members but desired more time for interaction.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> "Getting to know my team members and more time with them."
Training delivery	Difficulties were expressed with following training due to technical setups and pacing, suggesting a need for improved delivery.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> "It was difficult to follow along in the February 28th trainings - I wasn't working on a dual monitor..."

Key Themes	Recommended Improvements	Quotes
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> "One thought that could save time...develop their own forest carbon questions."
Preparation for CodeFest	Suggestions were made for better preparation prior to events, like having detailed walkthroughs and enforcing pre-event trainings.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> "More walkthroughs of code" "Day one could have been smoother if training was required."
Structure	Participants noted that the codefest could benefit from streamlined training and more structured group activities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> "Potentially they could be pared down to just one or maybe two trainings..." "A bigger emphasis on discovering topics and possibly finding a way for people to self assemble."
Technical support	There was a call for more support during technical tasks, like using GitHub and cloud-based collaboration tools.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> "Give more traing on the cloud-based collaboration" "I think providing detailed written instructions and then hosting 'office hours' might be more effective..."

2024 Forest Carbon CodeFest Evaluation Outcomes

Participant Satisfaction with the ESIL CodeFest

78% of respondents were **satisfied** with the ESIL CodeFest overall (50% “Very Satisfied;” 28% “Extremely Satisfied”).

With regards to CodeFest logistics, **100%** of participants **agreed overall** that communication about the meeting was effective, well-planned, well-designed, and that Slack was helpful for making meetings run more smoothly. A majority of participants agreed overall that the goals of sessions were well-communicated (89%), agendas were well-facilitated (84%), and that speakers and presenters were engaging (88%). 34% disagreed overall that the cyberinfrastructure was easy to make use of.

Thinking about the logistics for the Forest Carbon CodeFest, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? (n=18)

CodeFest Overall Highlights

The best parts of the ESIL CodeFest, according to respondents, are summarized into the following key themes:

Key Themes	Highlights
Networking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meeting others in the field/industry Collaboration and making friends, including meeting different people from across the country
Learning and Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learning about remote sensing tools (e.g., Google Earth Engine, QGIS) Diving into new research question In-depth insight into forest ecology through presentations
Team Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Effective collaboration within teams Shared ideas and problem-solving in groups
Event Organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leadership from the program coordinator Timely emails and instructions from the support team Structured approach for learning coding Dietary needs were easily accommodated
Resources and Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to Cyverse Various informative presentations
Diversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diversity of attendees and perspectives

In a final open-ended question, respondents shared additional feedback on the ESIL CodeFest. Themes and representative verbatim responses are included below:

Positive Feedback:

- **Valuable Learning Experience:** Attendees found the event interesting and appreciated the opportunity to participate.
- **Overall Positive Event Organization:** Despite some noted issues, the event was well-received for its organization and content, with thanks extended to the organizers.
- **Effective Engagement:** Participants enjoyed the engaging tasks and the chance to work on meaningful projects.

Feedback on Improvements:

- **Event Duration and Scheduling:** There was a consensus that the event was too short. Suggestions included extending it to five days or adding full days dedicated to specific tasks such as coding and analyses to manage the complexity better.
- **Financial and Administrative Handling:** Participants experienced significant issues with cost reimbursements, with some facing financial difficulties due to upfront payments that were not fully compensated. Clarity and efficiency in the reimbursement process were identified as critical areas needing attention.
- **Technical and Resource Accessibility:** There were problems with CyVerse permissions which consumed valuable coding time.
- **Group Dynamics and Learning Opportunities:** The assignment of roles based on existing expertise led to a lack of learning opportunities for some participants. Suggestions were made for forming groups based on interest to enhance learning and improve the group dynamic.
- **Structure for Group Work:** It was suggested that establishing teams around a question of interest and then re-balancing for diversity could allow more effective collaboration and learning.

Respondents’ Recommendations for Improvement to the CodeFest

CodeFest participants shared the most challenging parts of the CodeFest.

Key Themes	Highlights
Time Constraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event was too short for effective engagement • Needed more days for focused work • Time constraints hindered research and collaboration
Team Dynamics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulties in team collaboration due to different perspectives, experience levels, and interests • Challenges in aligning on a realistic research question
Technical and Tool Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data access issues, especially with external files and permissions • Challenges with CyVerse, such as establishing work and maintaining connection
Event Structure and Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre-event virtual meetings were helpful but insufficient

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guest speaker presentations ran over time, reducing work time on projects
Skill and Role Alignment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mismatch in coding skills within teams, affecting collaboration • Personal challenges in adapting to team's dominant programming language
Financial Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complications with travel expense reimbursements, leading to double taxation

Networking Connections and Collaboration

83% of respondents **agreed** that they felt better prepared for **community-building and knowledge exchanges** after participating in the CodeFest. **95%** of respondents indicated that they felt they had made **connections across disciplines and sectors** during the CodeFest.

83% of respondents **agreed** the event inspired them to **promote inclusion in scientific spaces and communities**.

95% of respondents indicated that they felt they had made **connections with the EDS community** during the CodeFest. However, only **39%** of respondents felt that they had made **connections with the AI community** during the CodeFest.

Respondents were asked if they made any new professional connections during the CodeFest. Eight respondents indicated that they **made professional connections or were hopeful for these connections at the CodeFest, mainly with the members of their project group**. Example quotes include:

- *“Yes, I am connected to my team member as well as ESIL team members and many other people from diverse fields.”*
- *“We're planning to continue the work we started with the team from this codefest and the team that started the work last year. We've already had one meeting, which is exciting.”*
- *“Yeah! Not exactly research related but a subset of the team shared quite a few hobbies, so it was fun connecting and chatting about those!”*
- *“Yes, I feel I got to know my team very well and will use those connections in the future.”*

Overall Learning and Use of Data Tools and Skills

The majority of respondents (**89%**) agreed that they **made use of ESIL’s Cyberinfrastructure** during the CodeFest.

There was lower agreement on the following topics:

- **72%** of respondents **agreed** that their **awareness of data sovereignty increased**, while 17% remained neutral and 11% disagreed.
- **74%** of respondents **agreed** that they **had opportunities for purposeful playtime for EDS exploration**, while 11% remained neutral and 11% disagreed.
- **74%** of respondents **agreed** that they had **increased their awareness of appropriate, respectful use of data**. However, 11% disagreed and 17% were neutral.

In an open-ended question, respondents were invited to elaborate on the previous question. Five respondents include comments. Their verbatim responses are listed below:

- *“I really liked our discussions of respectful practices in relation to indigenous communities and the presentation in our first virtual meeting brought up perspectives that I hadn’t realized before.”*
- *“I didn’t engage with the Cyverse or most of the provided data sources because of our groups topic and existing knowledgebase. I still learned about the different data types and skills in cloud computing, but I didn’t necessarily further my skills.”*
- *“I didn’t interact with the AI community, and I would argue that is not necessarily an connection that EDS needs in order to be effective.”*
- *“I learned a lot of respectful use of data during this code fest that had not been brought to my attention previously.”*
- *“Awareness to data sovereignty is a great take home for me.”*

Confidence in Working with Data Skills and Tools

Respondents were asked to reflect on their confidence before and after the CodeFest. They self-reported **higher confidence** after the CodeFest in **across all categories except for analyzing and visualizing data.**

Experience Working with Data Cubes

Participants were asked to “Please comment on the quality of the data cube, for example whether it was comprehensive, inspiring, useful, etc.” Common themes in participant responses are summarized below:

Data Accessibility and Utility:

- The ESIIIL data was readily accessible and generally easy to work with, which facilitated effective use by the participants.
- Additional resources such as Python code examples could enhance the experience by providing a more balanced approach to data usage.

Data Library and Support:

- The data library was described as comprehensive and useful, with on-call support highly appreciated by participants.
- Awareness of new datasets like GEDI was beneficial, though there was a desire for more time to explore such data.

Technical Issues and Limitations:

- Technical difficulties with CyVerse impacted the use of specific datasets, such as the disturbance data, limiting some participants' experience.
- The removal of certain files (e.g., EPA Southern Rockies shapefile) during the event caused frustration and hindered data usage.

Data Variety and Preparation:

- The availability of a wide range of data types, such as LANDFIRE data, was noted as inspiring and particularly valuable for forest management studies.
- Some data forms, like the GEDI vector format, did not fully satisfy all participants' needs for in-depth analysis.

Training and Additional Resources:

- A need for further training or guidance on incorporating additional data into tools like CyVerse was expressed to better answer specific research questions.
- Suggestions for improving data handling capabilities and possibly providing more structured training sessions were made.

Concepts, Data Skills, Tools, and Workflows Acquired

Participants were asked to “Please describe any new concepts, data skills, tools, or workflows that you learned about throughout the CodeFest (if any).” Responses (n = 12) are summarized into themes below:

Educational Value and Learning:

- Participants greatly valued the educational aspects, learning about the history, management, and current issues facing forests, particularly in the SW Rockies.
- New research questions and data sources were explored, enhancing participants' understanding and exposure to new information.

Skill Development in Technology and Data Handling:

- Practical skills were developed in using platforms like CyVerse, GitHub, and GIS tools (Google Earth Engine, QGIS).
- Participants learned how to integrate various technological tools for coding, managing repositories on GitHub, and interacting with cloud computing environments.

Collaboration and Real-Time Learning:

- Working collaboratively in real-time on platforms like GitHub was both challenging and rewarding, providing a hands-on experience in group coding and project workflows.
- The experience of using cloud-based infrastructures and participating in group projects highlighted the importance and effectiveness of collaborative learning environments.

Advanced Data Analysis and Application:

- Detailed learning about specific datasets like GEDI and practices in data interpolation, linear modeling, and using AI to refine broad data into more usable forms.
- Although some projects like applying AI tools to estimate narrow scope data from broad scope data encountered issues, the concept itself was found to be insightful and promising.

Introduction to New Resources and Tools:

- Many participants were introduced to a variety of new resources and datasets that were previously unfamiliar, broadening their resource base and technical knowledge.
- The experience also included learning how to use GitHub for diverse purposes such as building websites, which added to the versatile skill set gained during the event.

Sense of Belonging in the EDS Communities

Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were conducted to evaluate changes in attendee's the pre-survey and reflection survey responses about sense of belonging. There were 13 respondents with matched pre- and post-responses included in the analysis.

Before and after the CodeFest, attendees were asked to choose the picture that best described their “the current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of an Environmental Data Science (EDS) professional.” Results showed a no significant change in overlap **in their sense of belonging** compared to before the CodeFest, $Z = -0.5241.$, $p > .05$. However, note that the sample size in this case is so small that the data do not form a normal distribution and results should be interpreted with care.

Attendees were also asked to rate the extent to which they agreed with statements about their sense of belonging in the EDS communities.

There was no change in respondents' agreement with “**I belong to the EDS Community**” and only a slight, “**Being an EDS community member is an**

important part of my identity” ($p > 0.05$). However, note that the sample size in this case is so small that the data do not form a normal distribution and results should be interpreted with care.

Culture of Inclusion: General Respect and Respect for Expertise

A large majority of respondents agreed that **colleagues’ contributions were respected and valued (95-100%)**. A large majority of respondents (**89-94%**) also agreed that all group members **felt comfortable providing feedback and contributing opposing viewpoints**. However, 6% indicated that they disagreed that colleagues respected the expertise of others in the group and that all group members felt comfortable providing an opposing viewpoint.

100% of respondents agreed that individually they felt respected by colleagues, their contributions were valued, and that they handled disagreements constructively. A large majority (88%) of respondents agreed that their group respected their expertise, they felt comfortable providing feedback, and comfortable providing an opposing viewpoint.

Thinking about your own experiences during the Forest Carbon CodeFest, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? (n=17)

Group/Team Dynamics

Mentors: **87%** of respondents agreed that their **mentors provided helpful guidance** throughout the CodeFest.

Judges: **74%** of respondents agreed that the **judges provided helpful feedback**, and **81%** of respondents agreed that the **judges provided a fair assessment of each group's project** with 20% remaining neutral.

Team Members: **82%** of respondents agreed that their **team was effective**, however 6% within this group remained neutral and 6% disagreed or strongly disagreed. **82%** of respondents agreed that their **team had sufficient expertise**, however 6% within this group remained neutral and 12% disagreed.

CodeFest Artists in Residence

A unique part of the CodeFest was the inclusion of artists who helped participants think about their research. **33% of respondents agreed that involving artists helped their team think about their work in innovative ways and generate creative ideas**, although most (**58%**) were neutral. **75% agreed overall that working with artists enhanced their overall experience.**

Participant Reflections on the CodeFest Theme

The 2024 ESIIL CodeFest theme focused on data-intensive forest carbon research and Environmental Data Science (EDS). Participants were asked to comment on their thoughts about this topic after participating in the CodeFest. Below is a summary of their responses after the CodeFest with some representative quotes from respondents:

The event revealed significant untapped potential in computational resources and the opportunity for growth in open science through shared HPC hubs and data archives, which deeply impressed attendees. Participants recognized their limited prior knowledge, particularly in forest carbon research, but gained valuable skills in data access and analysis using advanced platforms like CyVerse and GitHub, enriching their ability to mentor and collaborate across disciplines. The discussions and presentations at the workshop highlighted the infancy of the field and the critical need for interdisciplinary collaboration to develop standardized metrics for meaningful carbon accounting. There's considerable excitement about the prospects of new research, especially with datasets like GEDI, despite challenges like potential duplications of effort among various stakeholders. Overall, the experience was enlightening, showing the extensive possibilities for new research in forest carbon dynamics and the impactful use of data science in environmental studies.

- *“I think there is huge untapped potential here, I am extremely impressed by the computational resources being put together and made available and feel there is a lot of room for growth and a lot of potential for accelerating open science in creating these shared resource HPC hubs with open data archives attached.”*
- *“I think that the field is still in its infancy and is a great space for interdisciplinary collaboration...”*

- *“This field has a lot of promise, but it needs to focus not only on obtaining new knowledge through brute-force data science, but also on empowering science via connections with government agencies, private land-owners, local community groups, tribal nations, and non-profits.”*
- *“After attending this event I realized how limited my knowledge were in forest carbon research and access to data. It was great to work with team who know how to use coding to access data and analyze using advance platform like cyverse and I also learn to use github. I have so much to share and mentor my students ... from what I have learned and use for research collaboration in my team from various disciplines.”*

CodeFest Overall Impacts and Innovation

The CodeFest as an Incubator of Ideas: respondents expressed that the CodeFest served as an incubator of ideas *To a Very Large Extent* (41%), *To a Large Extent* (18%), or *To a Moderate Extent* (35%) with an additional 6% indicating *To a Small Extent* and none *To a Very Small Extent*.

When asked to elaborate on this rating, respondents (n = 5) expressed both positive experiences and challenges during the ESIIIL CodeFest. During a collaborative session, a diverse group of individuals shared and developed a final idea through a dynamic exchange of perspectives. While the time constraints and data volume posed challenges, inspiring presentations and creative solutions emerged, highlighting the effectiveness of group collaboration despite the focus on task completion within smaller teams. The event provided participants, including the speaker, with substantial new material and methodologies, particularly in data analysis. However, the overall potential for generating groundbreaking new directions for EDS was somewhat restricted by the limited time available for ideation before implementation. Example quotes are included below:

- *“We bounced ideas back and forth and I hope all felt we contributed to the final idea's creation, it was interesting getting everyone's perspectives together.”*
- *“I really enjoyed others presentations and I think that was inspiring, and in my group I learned about new methods of data analysis, but within my team we were more focused on tasks than incubation of ideas.”*
- *“Given the time constraints and volume of data, it was hard to think really outside the box. But some groups came up with some very creative ideas in very little time, which was cool to see!”*
- *“I personally have a lot of great material to dive into following the codefest, but I wouldn't say that the codefest generated a lot of useful new directions for EDS in general.”*
- *“There was a limited time to generate ideas before we had to actually get started, so the potential to generate totally novel ideas or approaches was limited by feasibility.”*

Motivation to Continue Working on Ideas: respondents expressed that they were **motivated to continue working on the ideas that were explored during the CodeFest** *To a Very Large Extent* (12%), *To a Large Extent* (41%), or *To a Moderate Extent* (35%), with another 6% indicating *To a Small Extent* and 6% *To a Very Small Extent*.

Future Plans (n=7): Participants were asked to comment on how they plan to use what they learned at the CodeFest in their future work. The responses from various participants highlight their diverse experiences and intentions following a collaborative project. One individual plans to enhance the accessibility of environmental datacubes and integrate advanced analytical techniques within the Forest Service, aiming for publication of the project. Although another participant found their project's focus unrelated to their main job, they valued the learning experience. Collectively, there is a strong interest in applying the newly acquired methodologies to

further educational pursuits, including potential PhD research in forestry, reflecting a commitment to advancing their professional skills and contributing to their fields. Quotes are provided below:

- *“Looking to create accessible environmental datacubes for others to use.”*
- *“I plan to use the analytical techniques that I learned.”*
- *“I hope to see the project we started through to publication.”*
- *“I work for ... a federal agency, and to the best of my knowledge we are not making use of any of these tools whatsoever. I plan to integrate these tools into my ongoing work explaining how data science can help the agency.”*
- *“Working with large datacubes will be something I continue to pursue.”*
- *“My teams' question was very focused and not really related to my day job, so I probably won't use this in the future. But it was still interesting!”*
- *“I hope to use some of these ideas as I pursue further education in forestry. PhD ideas were definitely swirling around.”*

References

- King, J. A., & Stevahn, L. (2012). *Interactive evaluation practice: Mastering the interpersonal dynamics of program evaluation*. Sage Publications.
- Shulha, L. M., Whitmore, E., Cousins, J. B., Gilbert, N., & al Hudib, H. (2016). Introducing evidence-based principles to guide collaborative approaches to evaluation: Results of an empirical process. *American*

Appendix: Evaluation Surveys

ESIIL PreSurvey Forest Carbon CodeFest March 2024

What is your name?

How did you learn about the ESIIL Forest Carbon CodeFest? Select all that apply.

- I attended the ESIIL Innovation Summit.
- I received an email from ESIIL@colorado.edu.
- LinkedIn
- Twitter/X
- ESIIL's website
- Word of Mouth - I heard from others about it
- An online forum or Slack channel (e.g. ECOLOG, AISES); if so, which one:

- Other:

What would you like to get out of your participation in the ESIIL Forest Carbon CodeFest? Please share 1-3 goals or expectations you have for this event.

You completed an application for the ESIIL Forest Carbon CodeFest event that included questions about your expertise and expectations for the event. Is it okay with you if we include your application responses in this evaluation study? (Data will be de-identified after the data collection period ends.)

- Yes
- No

Please consider the following definition of Environmental Data Science (EDS) when answering the questions in this survey: We define EDS broadly to include any work where big data is used to drive discovery, solutions and science to understand our environment. It is highly transdisciplinary, including aspects of the natural and social sciences (that explore the environment and human interactions) and data sciences

We are interested in learning about how your participation in the ESIIL events is shaping your perception of yourself as a member of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community. Select the picture that best describes the current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community.

Please indicate to what extent you agree with the following statements.

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neutral	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree	N/A
I belong to the EDS community.	<input type="radio"/>					
Being an EDS community member is an important part of my identity.	<input type="radio"/>					

ESIIL holds inclusion as a core principle and method for diversifying environmental data science at a time when society needs all perspectives, and science needs to serve all. The questions below invite you to provide demographic information that will help us better understand who currently participates in ESIIL activities and events and will inform our approaches to inclusion to better serve ESIIL’s mission. You are never required to provide this information. All questions contain a “Prefer not to answer” option.

Which of the following best describes your current career stage?

- Student (I am an undergraduate student or graduate student)
- Early Career (I am a post-doctoral fellow or have 0 to 5 years of professional experience.)
- Mid-Career (I have 6 to 15 years of professional experience.)
- Senior (I have more than 15 years of professional experience.)
- Other. Please describe. _____
- Prefer not to answer

What best describes the organization in which you work?

- Academic (higher education)
- Government: Federal
- Government: State
- Government: Local
- Industry
- K-12 or Informal Education
- Non-profit: Research and Development (FFRDC/National Labs/etc)
- Non-profit: other
- Private for-profit
- Tribal organization
- Self
- Other: _____
- Prefer not to answer

Are you affiliated with an academic institution?

- Yes
- No
- Unsure

Display This Question:

If Are you affiliated with an academic institution? = Yes

With which type of academic institution are you affiliated? Select all that apply.

- Community College/ 2-yr College
- Professional Program
- American and Native American Pacific Islander-Serving Institutions (AAPISI)
- Hispanic Serving Institution (HSI)
- Historically Black University (HBCU)
- Tribal College or Tribal-Serving Institution (TCU)
- Minority Serving Institution (MSI)
- Primarily Undergraduate Serving
- Undergraduate and Graduate Serving
- Research Intensive (R1/R2/etc)
- If none of the options fit, how would you describe the main organization you are affiliated with? _____
- Prefer not to answer

Display This Question:

If Are you affiliated with an academic institution? = No

How would you describe the main organization you are affiliated with?

Which of the following categories best describes your highest level of education?

- Some high school
- High school diploma or equivalent
- Vocational training
- Some college
- Associate degree (e.g. AA, AE, AFA, AS, ASN)
- Bachelor's degree (e.g. BA, BBA, BFA, BS)
- Some graduate work
- Master's degree (e.g. MA, MBA, MFA, MS, MSW)
- Applied or professional graduate degree (e.g. MD, DDS, JD)
- Doctoral degree (e.g. EdD, PhD)
- Not listed, please specify: _____
- I prefer not to answer

In what field and what year did you receive your highest degree?

What are the main professional societies to which you belong? Please select up to 5 professional societies from the drop-down menu, or type in the organization's full name if it is not listed.

Professional Society #1 _____

Professional Society #2 _____

Professional Society #3 _____

Professional Society #4 _____

Professional Society #5 _____

In which disciplinary field(s) of Environmental Data Science do you MAINLY work? Select all that apply.

- Environmental Science
- Computer/Data Science
- Chemistry / Biochemistry
- Social Science
- Economics
- Geoscience (Geology, Geography)
- Biological science
- Engineering
- Math
- Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning
- Other. Please specify. _____
- Prefer not to answer
- I don't work in an EDS field

We collect demographic information for three reasons: 1) to hold ourselves accountable for meeting our diversity goals, including to provide opportunities for voices that may not have been well represented in Environmental Data Sciences; 2) to ensure that ESIIIL meets the needs of a national community; 3) to be able to share aggregated, non-identified data in publications and reports; and 4) to conduct basic research on the social dynamics and outcomes of scientific collaborations and teams. You are never required to provide this information. All questions contain a “Prefer not to answer” option.

How do you currently describe your gender identity? Select all that apply.

- Woman
- Man
- Transgender
- Non-binary
- Gender non-conforming
- I identify as: _____
- I prefer not to answer

Do you identify as LGBTQ+?

LGBTQ+ includes (but isn't limited to) Agender, Aromantic, Asexual, Bisexual, Gay, Gender fluid, Gender non-conforming, Genderqueer, Intersex, Lesbian, Non-binary, Pansexual, Queer, Questioning, Trans, and Two spirit.

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to answer

Please select the racial/ethnic group(s) with which you identify. Select all that apply.

- Black, African American, or African
- American Indian or Alaska Native
- Asian or Asian American
- White, Caucasian, European, or European American
- Hispanic or Latinx; Hispanic or Latinx American
- Middle Eastern or North African; Middle Eastern or North African American
- Pacific Islander or Native Hawaiian
- Not listed, please specify: _____
- I prefer not to answer

We realize the above options for describing your racial and ethnic identity are not all inclusive. If you would like, you can tell us how you would prefer to describe your racial and ethnic identity.

Do you identify as having a disability or as being neurodiverse?

Disability/neurodiversity status includes (but is not limited to) those who are Deaf or have serious difficulty hearing; Blind or have serious difficulty seeing even when wearing glasses; those who have serious difficulty walking or climbing stairs; those with a serious disability related to a physical condition; those with a serious disability related to a mental or emotional condition, or those with known conditions of neurodiversity.

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to answer

To help us develop ESIL so that the project is as accessible as possible, please describe any accommodations that would be needed for you to participate optimally in virtual and in-person events:

Are you a member of the U.S. Armed Forces?

- Yes, I am currently serving
- Yes, I am a Veteran
- No, I am not a member of the U.S. Armed Forces
- I prefer not to answer

Have either of your parents or guardians completed a Bachelor's degree or higher (Masters, PhD)?

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to answer

Where do you live?

- I live in the United States (If yes, please specify your home zip code:)

- I am outside the United States (If yes, in which country are you located?)

- I prefer not to answer

Where is your place of work located?

- Place of work is in the United States (If yes, please specify your home zip code:)

- Place of work within a Tribal Nation (If yes, please list the Tribal Nation)

- Place of work is outside the United States (If yes, in which country are you located?)

- I prefer not to answer

ESIIL Reflection Survey Forest Carbon CodeFest March 2024

We would like to invite you to share your feedback on the ESIIL Forest Carbon CodeFest. Your participation in the survey is optional, but your feedback is greatly appreciated. Your responses will be summarized and shared with the organizers to facilitate improvements to future events. The survey will take approximately 10 - 15 minutes to complete.

What is your name?

To what extent do you agree or disagree that the following training webinars prepared you for the Forest Carbon CodeFest?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	I did not attend this event.
Introduction, teamwork, open science, and data sovereignty (February 21)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Skills for cloud-based collaboration (February 28)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data availability and forest carbon perspectives (March 7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

In what ways could the pre-CodeFest Trainings be improved?

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about your experience at the ESIL Forest Carbon CodeFest?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
The required level of coding ability advertised for this event was appropriately represented and accurate.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I had adequate coding skills to contribute during the event.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I had adequate non-coding skills and knowledge to contribute during the event.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

What were the best parts about the ESIL Forest Carbon CodeFest?

What were the most challenging parts of the ESIL Forest Carbon CodeFest?

Overall, how satisfied were you with the ESIL Forest Carbon CodeFest?

- Extremely Satisfied
- Very Satisfied
- Moderately Satisfied
- Slightly Satisfied
- Not at all Satisfied

The ESIIIL CodeFest theme focused on data-intensive forest carbon research and Environmental Data Science (EDS). Please share your thoughts about this topic after participating in the ESIIIL CodeFest.

Thinking about the logistics for the Forest Carbon CodeFest, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
Communication about the meeting was effective	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Meeting was well-planned	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Goals of sessions were clearly communicated	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Meeting was well-facilitated	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Agenda was well-designed	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Speakers and presenters were engaging	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cyberinfrastructure (CI) was easy to make use of	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Using Slack helped the meeting to run more smoothly	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Thinking about the outcomes of the Forest Carbon CodeFest overall, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about this event?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	N/A
I created new connections across disciplines and sectors.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I made connections with the EDS community.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I made connections with community partners.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am better prepared for community-building and knowledge exchange through new collaborations.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I was inspired by this event to promote inclusion in scientific spaces and communities.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please elaborate on your responses to the previous question.

Thinking about the outcomes of the Forest Carbon CodeFest overall, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about this event?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	N/A
I furthered my skills related to Environmental Data Science (EDS).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I had opportunities to explore and play with environmental datasets during the coding event.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I made connections with the AI community.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I used ESIL's Cyberinfrastructure during the coding event.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I increased my awareness of data sovereignty.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I increased my awareness of appropriate, respectful use of data.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please elaborate on your responses to the previous question.

As part of the Forest Carbon CodeFest, you worked with an ESIL data cube or data library. Please comment on the quality of the data cube or data library (for example whether it was comprehensive, inspiring, useful, etc.).

Please consider the following definition of Environmental Data Science when answering the questions in this survey: We define EDS broadly to include any work where big data is used to drive discovery, solutions and science to understand our environment. It is highly transdisciplinary, including aspects of the natural and social sciences (that explore the environment and human interactions) and data sciences.

We are interested in learning about how your participation in ESIIIL events is shaping your perception of yourself as a member of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community. Select the picture that best describes the current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community.

Please indicate to what extent you agree with the following statements.

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neutral	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree	N/A
I belong to the EDS community.	<input type="radio"/>					
Being an EDS community member is an important part of my identity.	<input type="radio"/>					

Please describe any new **concepts, data skills, tools, or workflows** that you learned about throughout the Forest Carbon CodeFest (if any).

Did you complete any work off Cyverse?

- Yes
- No

Display This Question:

If Did you complete any work off Cyverse? = Yes

Where did you perform your computing? Please explain why you chose to use this platform for your computation, as an alternative to CyVerse.

Please provide two responses for each statement to tell us **how confident you feel** in doing these tasks independently **AFTER you finished participating** in the Forest Carbon CodeFest **compared to BEFORE participating** in the Forest Carbon CodeFest.

	CONFIDENCE AFTER					CONFIDENCE BEFORE				
	Very Confident	Moderately Confident	Slightly Confident	Not Confident	N / A	Very Confident	Moderately Confident	Slightly Confident	Not Confident	N / A
Working with data cubes or data libraries	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Creating reproducible workflows	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Collaborating with new people	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Coding with other people	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Documenting code so others can use it	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Running code in the cloud	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Envisioning the future of EDS research with Forest Carbon	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Managing data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Analyzing or visualizing data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	

Thinking about the **Forest Carbon CodeFest overall**, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
Colleagues showed a general respect for one another	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Colleagues respected the expertise of others in the group	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The contributions of all group members were valued	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
All group members felt comfortable providing feedback	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
All group members felt comfortable providing an opposing viewpoint or interpretation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Disagreements were handled constructively	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The meeting code of conduct was consistently implemented	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Slack was an effective way to communicate with peers and work more efficiently	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Thinking about **your own experiences** during the Forest Carbon CodeFest, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
I felt respected by my colleagues	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Others in my group respected my expertise	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt my contributions were valued	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt comfortable providing feedback	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt comfortable providing an opposing viewpoint or interpretation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I handled disagreements constructively	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
My team worked well together	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My team was effective	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My team has sufficient expertise to meet our goals	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The mentor(s) provided helpful guidance for my team	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Judges provided fair assessments of each group's project	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The feedback judges provided was helpful	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? (If you or your group did not interact with artists during the CodeFest, please select "N/A.")

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
Involving artists in the CodeFest helped my team to think about our work in innovative ways.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Involving artists in the CodeFest helped my team to generate creative ideas.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Working with artists at the CodeFest enhanced my overall experience.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please elaborate on your response to the previous question.

Have you made new connections or research collaborations during the Forest Carbon CodeFest? If so, please elaborate.

To what extent did the Forest Carbon CodeFest serve as an incubation of ideas?

- To a Very Large Extent
- To a Large Extent
- To a Moderate Extent
- To a Small Extent
- To a Very Small Extent

Please elaborate on your answer to the previous question.

To what extent are you motivated to continue working on the ideas that were explored during the Forest Carbon CodeFest?

- To a Very Large Extent
- To a Large Extent
- To a Moderate Extent
- To a Small Extent
- To a Very Small Extent

How do you plan to use what you learned at the Forest Carbon CodeFest in your future work?

Please share any other feedback you have about the Forest Carbon CodeFest.

If you did not take the Forest Carbon CodeFest pre-survey, please respond to this question:

You completed an application for the Forest Carbon CodeFest event that included questions about your expertise and expectations for the event. Is it okay with you if we include your application responses in this evaluation study? (Data will be de-identified after the data collection period ends.)

- Yes
- No